

Maximum Entropy Subject to a Constraint In Terms of a Gradient of Probability

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The process of maximizing Shannon's entropy $-P(x) \ln(P(x))$ subject to an a priori constraint $G(x)P(x)$ (where $G(x)$ is some function) is often thought of in terms of maximizing arrangements subject to the bias of the a priori constraint. Ultimately, however, one obtains an equation linking $1 + \ln(P(x))$ to (Lagrange multiplier) $G(x)$ which in turn becomes an equation demonstrating the value of the gradient of $P(x)$, i.e. dP/dx in terms of (Lagrange multiplier) $P(x)G(x)$.

In the case of $G(x)=1$, i.e. probability is normalized to 1, there is no bias and hence the gradient is 0. Thus a coin or a die have equal probabilities. In short, the maximization of entropy yields a kind of balance equation for dP/dx (flux type term) with $G(x)P(x)$ Lagrange Multiplier ((1)). Instead of thinking of entropy in terms of maximizing arrangements, one may think in terms of this balance equation. $G(x)P(x)$, although formally the constraint in the problem, is associated with a different type of constraint, namely the particular balance which results. As a result, a problem which has an a priori balance condition, (and perhaps no a priori Integral $dxG(x)P(x)$ constraint) may, in fact, be consistent with the maximization of entropy subject to this constraint. The balance, however, has to be of the form of ((1)). Secondly, maximization of entropy must allow $P(x)$ to change freely except for the $G(x)P(x)$ constraint.

In classical mechanics, there is a specific situation in which such a balance exists, namely that of a statistical mechanical gas with a potential. Gas particles have kinetic energy, but the average kinetic energy of a single particle is $.5T$ (one dimension or $1.5T$ in three dimensions) and its average pressure is T . Average kinetic energy for a particle is not a function of x . This allows $P(x)$ to adjust without an x dependent kinetic energy constraint. There is a natural balance expected from Newtonian mechanics, but maximization of entropy with the constraint $G(x)P(x)$ also leads to a balance: $dP/dx = \text{Lagrange multiplier } P(x) dG/dx$.

If these two balances equate for some $G(x)$, the expected Newtonian force-pressure balance is equivalent to maximization of entropy subject to a special constraint which creates a certain gradient dP/dx . If instead of using Shannon's entropy, one tries to maximize a different function of $P(x)$ subject to the same constraint, one obtains a different balance equation. The key here is that the balance is based on dP/dx (which is proportional to the difference of $P(x)$ on the two sides of a 1 dimensional box of width dx is equated with $-P(x)$ (Lagrange multiplier) dG/dx . In other words, $P(x)/\text{Lagrange multiplier}$ seems to exert a kind of pressure on each side of dx , while $P(x)$ inside dx multiplied by $-dG/dx$ tries to balance this pressure. This statistical result (for Shannon's entropy) seems to be akin to two scenarios. One is an impulse picture which acts on the two sides of dx which each particle having an average $1/\text{Lagrange multiplier}$ impulse and a Force multiplied by density picture akin to work. These are two key concepts in Newtonian mechanics and they appear naturally in the maximum Shannon's entropy approach. The second scenario is a free particle wavefunction $P(x)=\exp(ipx)$, where $p dP/dx$ is a probability flux which balances an impulse p multiplied by $i P(x)$. Thus, we argue that maximization of Shannon's entropy is akin to a pressure force balance.

What about the quantum bound case? In such a situation, one has a conservation of energy equation which follows from special relativistic invariance, i.e. the Klein-Gordon equation. (In the nonrelativistic limit, this yields the time-independent Schrodinger equation for a constant E .)

Here $\langle KE(x) \rangle$ average is a function of x . One cannot arbitrarily change $P(x)$ linked to a constraint on $V(x)$ i.e. use a balance equation equivalent to maximum entropy except in a case in which kinetic energy and potential energy are decoupled, namely the quantum oscillator. In such a situation, maximum entropy may be applied to the ground state and is linked with a kind of pressure-force balance as we demonstrate.

Maximization of Shannon's Entropy Subject to a Constraint and Balance

Maximization of Shannon's entropy is often associated with expressing entropy as the \ln of the number of unique permutations of a set of N particles with an attribute, say energy E , distributed in such a way that $n(e_i)$ is the number of particles with energy e_i . Shannon's entropy is maximized subject to the constraint $\sum_i e_i n(e_i)$. As a result, one thinks in terms of a maximum number of arrangements subject to the constraint. We suggest that maximization of entropy subject to a constraint ultimately leads to an expression for dn/de i.e. a derivative value showing how the probability (or number of particles) changes from one e_i to another.

For example, for a coin or die, the constraint is $\sum_i P(i)=1$ so maximum entropy leads to no slope change i.e. each probability is the same.

Shannon's entropy for $P(x)$, subject to a constraint $\int G(x)P(x)dx$ where $G(x)$ is some function, leads to a balance equation of the form:

$$1 + \ln(P(x)) = -1/T G(x) \text{ where } 1/T \text{ is the Lagrange multiplier } \quad ((2))$$

$$\text{Taking } d/dx \text{ gives: } dP/dx / P = -1/T dG/dx \quad ((3))$$

Shannon's entropy maximization (i.e. using \ln of the number of permutations possible) yields a specific relationship for dP/dx . In fact, ((3)) is a kind of balance equation with dP/dx proportional to the change in $P(x)$ and $P(x+dx)$. This is counterbalanced by $P(x)$ within dx multiplied by $-dG/dx$. Maximization of Shannon's entropy, may be thought of as balance perhaps linked to some kind of probability flux. dP/dx , which in turn is related to the difference in $P(x)$ and $P(x+dx)$. One may have a physical problem with a balance involving $d/dx \ln(B(x))$, where $B(x)$ is some function, and this may have an association with Shannon's entropy maximization. One does not simply need to think in terms of the constraint $\int dx G(x)P(x)$. In fact, this constraint may not be particularly apparent in some problems for which the balance is apparent.

In particular, we consider the idea of mechanical balance from Newtonian physics. If forces acting on a particle balance and there is no net torque, the particle is balanced. In such a case, force (due to an existing potential) acts on the center of mass, for example, and impulse hits occur at surfaces. For a tiny one-dimensional box of size dx , impulse hits are along the two sides at x and $x+dx$. If there are $n(x)$ particles at x , each with an average pressure of $2T$, the net difference of impulse hits (i.e. pressure) is: $2T dn/dx$. If a force exists due to a potential, this acts on $n(x)$ i.e. $-dV/dx n(x)$. Balancing yields:

$$2T dP/dx = -dV/dx P(x) \text{ where } n \text{ is proportional to } P(x), \text{ probability } \quad ((4))$$

This mechanical problem, extended to include average pressure, is of the identical form of the maximization of Shannon's entropy subject to the constraint $\int dx V(x)P(x)$ ((3)).

In general, one would not think of such a constraint as being an a priori known value and would need to fix the Lagrange multiplier instead of using $-1/T$ where T is temperature. Temperature follows from a separate maximization of Shannon's entropy based on kinetic energy with T being the Lagrange multiplier for that problem.

We suggest that the particular form of the pressure balancing force problem is exactly of the form of a maximization of Shannon's entropy with a suitable constraint. A key idea, however, is that there are actually two maximizations occurring, one linked to kinetic energy and the other to $V(x)$, with the kinetic energy part not introducing any function of x . It simply yields T , temperature, which is the average pressure of a single particle. This allows for $P(x)$ to adjust subject to maximization of Shannon's entropy, i.e. create its pressure-force balance.

This approach holds for any $V(x)$ in classical statistical mechanics. We suggest that maximization of Shannon's entropy is really an approach which yields dP/dx in terms of a (Lagrange multiplier) $G(x)P(x)$ and so is identical to certain balances which are observed in nature.

Quantum Mechanical Bound State Scenario

What happens in a quantum bound state scenario? We argue that a free particle is described by a two dimensional probability $\exp(ipx)$ which follows from the maximization of Shannon's entropy $-P(x) \ln(P(x))$ subject to the periodic constraint $\int p \times P(x)$. This itself yields a balance equation of the form:

$$dP/dx = ip P(x) \quad ((5))$$

for the probability gradient for a Shannon's entropy problem. Here the function $G(x)=x$ and the Lagrange multiplier is set at ip . "p" (momentum) is proportional to an impulse. In fact, the form $\exp(ipx)$ is associated with a square root flux. Thus, probability at x and $x+dx$ balances the impulse multiplied by $P(x)=\exp(ipx)$. This suggests that a particle (or photon) moves with probability in a kind of unusual mechanical balance with impulse (momentum).

((5)) may be generalized to E,t to yield $\exp(-iEt)$. The product is: $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$. If $-Et+ipx$ is considered to be Lorentz invariant as seen from frames moving with average velocity= x/t =constant, then:

$$-Et+px \text{ and } -EE+pp \text{ are Lorentz invariants i.e. } -EE+pp = momo (c=1) \quad ((6))$$

If a potential $V(x)$ is present, one may replace E with $E-V(x)$, but pp is now an average i.e.

$$\langle pp \rangle = \{ \text{Sum over } p \quad pp a(p) \exp(ipx) \} / \{ \text{Sum over } p a(p) \exp(ipx) \} \quad ((7))$$

This problem is not thought of in terms of Newtonian force-pressure balance, but in terms of Newtonian kinetic energy plus $V(x)$ balance. One may note that ((6)) with ((7)) is the

Klein-Gordon equation and that in the nonrelativistic limit it yields the Schrodinger time-independent equation if E is a constant.

One may note that ((5)) still implies a balance of dP/dx with $ipP(x)$ and so there is also an average balance i.e.

$$-i \frac{dW/dx}{W} = \langle p \rangle \quad \text{where } W(x) = \sum_p a(p) \exp(ipx) = \text{wavefunction} \quad ((8))$$

What if one considers spatial probability $P_s(x)$ as in the classical statistical mechanical case? In such a case: $P_s(x) = W^*(x)W(x)$ ((9)). $W(x)$, however, is linked with x contributions from kinetic energy and potential energy in the Schrodinger time-independent equation. The approach of classical statistical mechanics, i.e. the force pressure balance is not expected to hold unless somehow kinetic energy and potential energy may be considered independent. There is a special case in quantum mechanics for which this happens, namely the quantum oscillator. Due to the symmetry of pp and xx from $V(x) = .5kxx$, average kinetic energy equals average potential energy. If one considers $P_s(x)$ as being associated with the maximization of Shannon's entropy subject to the constraint $\int dx V(x) P_s(x)$, then the balance equation is:

$$dP_s/dx = -dV(x/dx) P_s(x) \text{ Lagrange multiplier} \quad ((9)) \quad \text{or}$$

$$dP_s/dx/P_s = 2 \frac{dW/dx}{W} \text{ Lagrange multiplier} \quad ((10))$$

The average impulse balances the classical force $-kx$. This occurs for the ground state of a quantum oscillator. This situation, then, seems to be equivalent to a maximization of Shannon's entropy for $P_s(x)$ because it is not coupled to kinetic energy through x , but only through total energy E , which takes the place of T , temperature.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that although one may think of Shannon's entropy as being the \ln of the number of unique permutations and hence its maximization subject to a constraint, a kind of maximization of arrangements, we suggest a different view. We argue that maximization of Shannon's entropy $-P(x) \ln(P(x))$ subject to the constraint $G(x)P(x)$ may be followed by taking d/dx of the result. This leads to a flux balance type of equation i.e. $dP/dx = -(\text{Lagrange multiplier}) dG/dx P(x)$. This balance is of the identical form of impulse hits creating pressure on two sides of a box dx with $-dV/dx P(x)$ being a balancing force inside. Another example is $\exp(ipx)$, the free particle wavefunction. $dP/dx = ip P(x)$ so it is almost as if probability difference at the sides of dx balances the impulse p multiplied by $P(x)$. In other words, a free particle moves in a kind of balance- equilibrium. For both of these scenarios, kinetic energy does contribute a term linked x . In the pressure case, it contributes T , temperature, which is the average pressure of a single particle in a Maxwell-Boltzmann gas.

In the case of a quantum bound state, $\exp(ipx)\exp(-iEt)$ should be invariant as seen in a moving frame. This leads to the Lorentz invariant $-Et+px$, but also to $-EE+pp=momo$ (cc). For $E \rightarrow E-V(x)$, one must use an average for pp i.e. $\{\sum_p a(p)\exp(ipx) pp\} / \{\sum_p a(p)\exp(ipx)\}$. This yields the Klein-Gordon equation which becomes the time-independent

Schrodinger equation in the nonrelativistic limit for E constant. In this case, the kinetic energy term is linked with x and one cannot use the maximization of $P(x)=W(x)W(x)$, where $W(x)=\text{Sumover } p \ a(p) \exp(ipx)$, unless kinetic energy and potential energy become decoupled. The quantum oscillator, however, allows for such decoupling. One may consider maximization of Shannon's entropy for $P(x)$ in this case and find that the balance equation applies to the ground state.